

Supplementary material for
**Comparison of Non-Parametric Interpolation Techniques
for Sparsely Measured Binaural Room Impulse Responses**
JAES (2024)

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1 Perceptual Analysis - Additional Information

1.1 Q-Q Plots for rejected normality

Figure S1: Normal quantile-quantile plots for 14 of 96 cases where a Lilliefors test for normality failed to reject the null hypothesis. The solid line denotes the ideal normal distribution.

1.2 Pairwise Emmeans Comparison

Comparison	Estimate	SE	df	t.ratio	p.value
Blend - DTW	-17.45	3.28	207	-5.319	< .0001 _v
Blend - LISHPh	-15.09	3.28	207	-4.601	< .0001*
Blend - SARITA	-29.80	3.28	207	-9.087	< .0001*
DTW - LISHPh	2.36	3.28	207	0.719	0.8896
DTW - SARITA	-12.36	3.28	207	-3.768	0.0012*
LISHPh - SARITA	-14.71	3.28	207	-4.486	0.0001*

Table 1: Emmeans comparison for IP Method at 30° Resolution with only vocal and music stimulus

Comparison	Estimate	SE	df	t.ratio	p.value
Blend - DTW	-12.000	3.31	207	-3.629	0.0020*
Blend - LISHPh	-12.411	3.31	207	-3.753	0.0013*
Blend - SARITA	-20.821	3.31	207	-6.297	< .0001*
DTW - LISHPh	-0.411	3.31	207	-0.124	0.9993
DTW - SARITA	-8.821	3.31	207	-2.668	0.0407*
LISHPh - SARITA	-8.411	3.31	207	-2.544	0.0563

Table 2: Emmeans comparison for IP Method at 40° Resolution with only vocal and music stimulus

Comparison	Estimate	SE	df	t.ratio	p.value
Blend - DTW	1.34	3.16	207	0.424	0.9744
Blend - LISHPh	-9.02	3.16	207	-2.853	0.0244*
Blend - SARITA	-11.20	3.16	207	-3.542	0.0027*
DTW - LISHPh	-10.36	3.16	207	-3.277	0.0067*
DTW - SARITA	-12.54	3.16	207	-3.966	0.0006*
LISHPh - SARITA	-2.18	3.16	207	-0.689	0.9011

Table 3: Emmeans comparison for IP Method at 60° Resolution with only vocal and music stimulus

Comparison	Estimate	SE	df	t.ratio	p.value
Blend - DTW	-0.786	3.25	207	-0.242	0.9950
Blend - LISHPh	-4.839	3.25	207	-1.488	0.4466
Blend - SARITA	-6.643	3.25	207	-2.042	0.1759
DTW - LISHPh	-4.054	3.25	207	-1.246	0.5981
DTW - SARITA	-5.857	3.25	207	-1.801	0.2759
LISHPh - SARITA	-1.804	3.25	207	-0.555	0.9452

Table 4: Emmeans comparison for IP Method at 90° Resolution with only vocal and music stimulus